

USING SLIDES IN DEVELOPING THE SPEAKING COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Annotation: This article discusses the use of slides as one of the tools of information technology in the development of students' speaking competence in primary-grade mother tongue and reading literacy classes.

Keywords: educational process, innovation, innovative technology, information technology, electronic manual.

Introduction: Today, in the era of rapid development of science and technology, in the conditions of globalization and integration, a strong competitive environment is being formed in all fields. This, in turn, puts new demands on the education system. Based on this, there was a need to create a national education system capable of withstanding global competition. Also, in order to bring the general secondary education to a new stage of development, taking into account advanced national and foreign experiences, international evaluation programs and requirements, the tasks of improving the curriculum, teaching methodology and the education quality assessment system were defined.

It is not a secret to any of us that the reforms being carried out in our country, especially the fundamental changes in the field of education, are for the education of the young generation who are mature and independent in all aspects. For this purpose, in order to improve the quality of education, the establishment of the "National Program of Personnel Training" and the "State Education Standard", strong attention to the issues of education and upbringing in primary grades, and in this way, they put a number of demands on teachers and pedagogues. The formation of a perfect personality is put on the agenda as an important social task of every era. The teacher should be able to effectively use information technology tools to develop students' speaking competence in the primary language and reading literacy classes. That is, when giving tasks to students, they should show their video and audio options, as well as pictures through slides. Then the students will have a broad understanding of the text, story, poem, fairy tale they have seen on the slides and heard the audio version, and their speech competence (listening comprehension,

speaking, reading, writing) will develop. In addition, based on his pedagogical skills, the teacher should also use interactive methods that increase students' speech during the lesson. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of the teacher and the student. This process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- forcing the student not to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, to create and search;
- to ensure that students have a constant interest in knowledge during the educational process;
- to increase the student's interest in knowledge independently with a creative approach to each issue;
- is to organize the activity of the teacher and the student in cooperation.

One such method is the "Interdependence" method. Students are shown subjects through slides. Pupils talk about the subject on the slide. For example: This is a tomato. Tomatoes are ripened on the shelf. The color is red, pink. Everyone loves it and eats it. Various salads can be prepared from tomatoes. Then the second student also talks about another subject on the slide and must say that his subject is related to the subject of the first student. This is the sun. When the sun rises, the air warms up. Tomatoes ripen from the hot sun. The interactive method is continued in this way. Through this method, students tell the information they have about the objects on the slide. After that, the teacher can give the students the task of writing a small text about the subjects shown on the slide in order to increase their speaking competence. Students create a story based on their life observations and independent creative research. Also, you can give an additional task to find the words that express the name of the object, its symbol, and action in this story. The teacher can use this method not only in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, but also in natural science, technology, mathematics, and fine arts classes. Or, depending on the requirements of the national program, interdisciplinary integration can be used. Mother tongue and reading literacy classes serve to expand children's ability to think, to express their thoughts fluently orally and in writing, to be able to think freely, to listen to the opinions of others, and to develop skills and abilities to communicate freely with members of society.

It is very important to develop students' interest in learning in the primary school education process. Because some students are more playful during this period. They should also be interested in the educational process. Therefore, it is appropriate to

use various methods and pedagogical technologies effectively and appropriately in the course of the lesson. Interactive methods greatly help to develop students' motivation to study. The use of interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is progressing day by day. Because, until that time, the education system in traditional education was aimed at acquiring only ready-made knowledge. According to the newly created National Program, the use of modern technologies in the educational system helps students to search for the acquired knowledge, learn independently, think, analyze, and even draw final conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher creates the ground for the development, formation, education and upbringing of the student as a perfect human being, and at the same time, the manager acts as a guide.

The use of slides, audio, and video lessons that are suitable for the subject of the lesson based on the requirements of each subject is the most important requirement today in improving the quality of the lessons in primary-grade mother tongue and reading literacy classes. A skilled pedagogue feels this and approaches each lesson creatively. A creative teacher inspires his students and strives to create something new in every lesson. In this process, the pedagogue uses information technology. For example, if the teacher is rehearsing a section in today's lesson, if they create slide, video and audio versions of riddles, poem, story, fairy tale and proverbs related to that section using information technology (computer), then the students will understand the topics covered well. It is a very convenient and interesting process to give the riddles in this process in the form of a video. When using a video puzzle, the following actions are performed:

- Several video clips are shown to the attention of students without explanations, which help to illustrate the essence of the topic being studied.
- Students explain what process is shown in each picture.
- They record the essence of their processes in their notebooks.
- They answer the questions asked by the teacher.
- A video will be shown on the computer.
- Students express their opinions about the topic of the video.

If we talk about the riddle in this process, the riddle is one of the most popular genres of folk oral poetic creation. Riddle is a genre found in the folklore of all peoples of the world. People's life, standard of living, culture, customs are expressed to a certain extent in riddles. The question that can be solved in a puzzle is expressed in a figurative form, and its meaning is hidden. The thing or event that is being found is embodied by likening it to another thing or event, comparing it with each other.

Riddles are sometimes in prose, often in poetic form, compositionally and rhythmically compact, simple and melodious. For example, A piece of bread, spread to the world (Moon). A white tablecloth covered the earth (Snow). (Bir parcha patir, olamga tatir (Oy). Oppoq dasturxon yer yuzini qoplagan (Qor). Teaching such riddles to students in the course of the lesson is an educational tool for increasing children's vocabulary, expanding their understanding and imagination about life and its events, perception and reasoning ability. The teacher can show these riddles to the students in the form of audio or video, slides. These riddles can be used in reading lessons outside the classroom. Studying outside the classroom is a process that is organized outside of the educational activities conducted with students. Extracurricular lessons are organized once a week for 1st-2nd graders, and once every two weeks for 3rd-4th graders. Using Uzbek folk riddles in these lessons is also an effective method. In this case, the teacher should use riddles that force the students to think and reason about nature, things, or logically. In addition, depending on the student's age, it is possible to use the riddles of the peoples of the world from the Internet. This gives students an understanding of the lifestyle, culture, and spirituality of the peoples of the world. In addition, the teacher should show the nation, the nation on the slide, which nation the riddle belongs to. This helps the child to develop an understanding of representatives of other peoples and nations.

Conclusion: In short, it can be said that every modern teacher living in the information age should be able to use information technologies. This allows the teacher to create a number of conveniences. Especially the quality of the lessons. A teacher will not have difficulties to find information in each lesson, if they know information technologies well. They try to create something new for the students by taking a different approach to each lesson. In fact, this is the requirement of the newly created National Program. Based on the requirements of the national program, it is necessary to effectively use information technologies in the development of students' speech competence in the primary language and reading literacy classes. Because it is necessary to choose new educational technology, methods and tools when studying each lesson topic. In order to achieve high results in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, it is necessary to plan the sequence of the lesson process in advance. Then every lesson will be of high quality and *effective*.

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